

COPING BEHAVIOR IN STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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***Abstract:** This article discusses a theoretical analysis of the concept of “coping”, and also analyzes research by various authors on coping behavior among students in the education system.*

***Key words:** Coping behavior, coping strategies, coping behavior, stress, student, students, modern education system.*

***Аннотация:** В этой статье рассматривается теоретический анализ к понятию «копинг», а также проанализированы исследования различных авторов копинг–поведение у студентов в системе образования.*

***Ключевые слова:** Копинг–поведение, копинг–стратегий совладающее–поведение, стресс, студент, студенчество, современная система образования.*

Introduction. A person is exposed to various stressful influences throughout his life, starting from early childhood, when any change can cause stress - new acquaintances, changes in living conditions, and so on. In the process of learning to adapt to new environments, a person observes his relatives, adults and others, developing his own methods of coping with stress. Determining the effectiveness of these methods helps him successfully adapt to the current circumstances.

Thus, it is important to develop adaptive coping mechanisms to cope with stress to ensure a more positive outlook in the future. The concept of “coping” comes from the English “to cope” - “to cope, to overcome.” The term “coping” was first used by L. Murphy in 1962 in a study of ways for children to overcome developmental crises. Subsequently, the study of coping mechanisms was closely related to studies of psychological stress [1].

The concept of “coping” refers to a set of psychological, behavioral and social efforts aimed at coping with difficulties caused by stressful situations. A significant feature is the active interaction of the individual with the environment in order to overcome difficulties.

“Coping” in Russian psychological literature is translated as “adaptive, coping behavior” or “psychological overcoming.” In 1966, Richard Lazarus, in his book *Psychological Stress and the Coping Process*, coined the term “coping” to describe conscious strategies for coping with stress and other anxiety-producing events. Lazarus and Folkman view coping as a dynamic interaction between a person and a situation, expressed in cognitive, behavioral and emotional actions aimed at overcoming external or internal contradictions. It involves a person’s efforts in coping with life’s challenges, which can be either successful or unsuccessful [1].

Methodology. V. Bityutskaya emphasizes that coping, unlike defense mechanisms, has plasticity and directionality, also takes into account the characteristics of a specific situation, includes processes of thinking and analyzing the situation, and is also characterized by high differentiation. While defense mechanisms are more rigid and automatic, coping involves a greater number of conscious reactions [2].

According to T.L. Kryukova - coping behavior differs from psychological defense in that it is a conscious strategy of action. It is aimed at eliminating the threat, overcoming interference and better adapting the person to the requirements of the situation. It is important to note that coping helps to transform the situation in accordance with the person’s intentions or, in cases where it is impossible to change circumstances, helps to withstand and endure them [3].

Stressful situations often arise both in everyday life and in the educational and pedagogical process. Therefore, it is important for future teachers and psychologists to master a variety of methods of coping with situations (coping behavior) and use effective strategies to overcome stress. It should be noted that in situations of stress, people resort to coping behavior. Thus, understanding the essence of stress and the ability to effectively use coping strategies is necessary not only for personal needs, but also for helping others overcome stress.

In her definitions of stress, Uzbekistan scientist E.Z. Usmanova refers to the definition of stress given in the transactional model as the most comprehensive:

Stress is an emotional state that always involves a relationship between the environment and the individual. During stress, contradictions arise between the demands of the situation and the resources (biological, psychological, social) of the individual. Stress strains a person's biopsychosocial resources [6].

Results. As an example, we present some studies devoted to the study of coping strategies in stressful situations among students. In the work of A.A. Kiseleva, V.V. Kozlov and T.A. Malykh, dedicated to the study of students at the Pedagogical Institute using the Methods of Coping Behavior by R. Lazarus and S. Folkman, differences were identified between future teachers and students of other specialties. According to the results, coping strategies of future teachers turned out to be more effective compared to students of other directions.

In some cases, when faced with a stressful situation, students attempt to solve the problem through the expression of negative emotions, hostility and conflict. Some students, experiencing emotional discomfort and not having a clear solution to the problem, prefer to deny the existence of difficulties, do not take specific actions, go into fantasy worlds, abuse food, drink alcohol, etc. in order to reduce emotional stress [4].

Discussion. In the studies of N.A. Sirota and V.M. Yaltonsky examines coping strategies of "problem-oriented" behavior among young people living in different social conditions. For young people from a relatively unfavorable environment, the

main motivation for making decisions is the desire to avoid failure. Research shows that youth preferentially develop a “social support seeking” strategy. Nevertheless, there are differences in the formation of this strategy among people brought up in different social conditions. Young people from a conditionally socially disadvantaged environment are characterized by more passive options for using these methods. They are limited only to accepting the help that the environment actively offers, and the willingness to accept it both from family and from friends and significant others [5].

Conclusions. Based on the studies described above, we can conclude that prospects are currently emerging for the development and implementation of programs to teach modern youth adaptive coping behaviors with difficult life situations in the process of receiving vocational education.

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